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PILLAI'S JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT RESEARCH

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Editorial

Pillais Institute Of Management Studies and Research has a unique mission of producing not just business ready managers , but leaders . The human assets of the institute are drawn from different faculty who have carved a niche for themselves in their respective fields. The students embody the qualities of a leader, which is evident from how they engage the people, look at issues , generate ideas and work towards transformational leadership .

At Pillai's we are aware that traditional approaches to management that may have worked in a booming economy are no longer sufficient to meet the demands of a changing market place. There is a necessity today that management students need to understand business principles not in abstraction but in the context of how they can be best practiced to address unfolding opportunities for the Indian economy. This is a possibility only when the students and teachers go beyond the curriculum and unearth new facets of managing men, matter, material and minds through research and studies. Research is a tool we can't live without.

Investment in research activities is as important as that of investment in any other allied areas of academics. The success of major world class universities of today can be attributed to their strong faith and matching support which they have been extending from time to time to the quality and need based research which goes to improve the contents, context and quality of learning. PIMSR believes in the value based research and the journal titled "Pillais Journal of Management Research" is one step towards that direction.

The institute welcomes articles, views and suggestions of the readers as they form the invaluable inputs for making it more meaningful , dynamic and for a better tomorrow.

With best wishes

Dr. G. Vijayaragavan

Director

THE SALES PROMOTION: A STUDY OF ITS INFLUENCES ON CUSTOMER PURCHASE INTENTION WITH REGARDS TO ORGANIZED RETAIL SERVICES

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to know about various sales promotional tools adopted by organized retail service industry, to analyze the influences of sales promotions on customer purchase intention and customer satisfaction level, with regards to sales promotional tools adopted by organized retail services providers. This study is about the 'more.' (A super market chain Aditya Birla Retail Limited). A personal interview has been taken from personnel of 'more.' to know sales promotional tools adopted by them. Samples of 200 respondents from Pune district of Maharashtra were surveyed utilizing a structured questionnaire, comprising specific questions pertaining to influences of sales promotions on customer purchase intention and satisfaction of respondents with regards to organized retail services. The results indicate that there are significant influences of sales promotion on customer purchase intention in case of organized retail services. Customers are satisfied with sales promotional tools adopted by organized retail service providers. This study also furnishes information about demographic variables and behavioral characteristics of customers of organized retail service industry.

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KEYWORDS

Organized Retail service, Sales Promotion, Customer Purchase Intention

Customer Satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Success of any organization relies upon the revenue generated from the market. A sale is the only source to generate this revenue in any industry. But retailing is an industry which drives a major part of revenue from its transaction with the final customers. Accordingly we can say that in this industry sales rely upon the customer purchase intention. Main cause behind the study of influences of sales promotions on customer purchase intention in organized retail industry is that sales promotion is a pillar of success in this industry because sales promotions not only entice the target customers psychologically and emotionally, but also plays a vital role to increase the sales, revenue and profit by increasing purchase frequency, quantity and money spend. Therefore, retailers ensure the implementation of innovative and efficient sales promotional strategies like- various schemes, discounts, prizes, contests, and free gifts etc at the right time to entice distinct target group of customers and beat competition. Sales promotions remedy to build loyalty, retain customers, entice first time users and repurchase, facilitate new product for trial, stimulate sales, revenue and profit, maintain sales in off season, increase level of customer satisfaction and play role of supplement to advertising.

This study is all about the sales promotional tools adopted by 'more.' (A super market of Aditya Birla Retail Limited). 'more.' offers a wide range of products like fruits & vegetables, groceries, personal

care, home care and general merchandise etc. with promise of Extra Quality, Extra Savings, Extra Rewards, Extra Care, and Extra Choice. Currently there are over 640 'more.' supermarket outlets across the country. 'more.' provides a world class pleasurable shopping experience to Indian customers in their very own neighborhood. More quality, more variety, more convenience, and more value are four delivery cornerstones of 'more.' 'more.' employs different schemes, rebates, prizes, gifts, contests to entice customers because they know, the customer satisfaction is important in reinforcing the customer's trust, commitment, repurchase intention and the financial performance of organization.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Kotler (2003) explained that consumer promotions have a direct impact on the purchase behaviour of the customers. And P. Raghuram *et. al.* (2004), conducted study and proved that sales promotion induces positive impact on short term sales. Michel *et. al.* (2001) investigates the cognitive affective behaviour of consumers on price promotions and finds that variety seeking business, perceived financial wellness and the brand loyalty influence of behaviour. Consumer price value equation is eroded if there is too much dependence on promotions. Schultz (2004)

Kwok, *et. al.* (2005) analyzed sales promotion effectiveness on ethnic group levels and found that there are significant differences in consumer cultural

values at an ethnic group level and despite these differences, ethnicity does not have a significant impact on responses to sales promotion. Monica C. *et. al.* (2008) found that loyalty card holders are less sensitive to regular prices but they are more sensitive for price promotions in certain product categories. Loyalty programme did not prompt heavy buyers to change their purchase behaviour, while for light buyers; loyalty programme broadened their relationship, pointed by Liu, Yuping (2007)

The existing literature focuses on general aspects of sales promotion, price promotion and its impact on consumer behaviour, less research work has been done on other promotional aspects.

Moreover, the study conducted in the area of sales promotion with regards to retail services has not been conducted in the Indian context. Therefore, this study.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To know about various sales promotional tools adopted by organized retail service industry.
2. To find out different demographic variables of customers of organized retail service industry.
3. To study the changing buying behaviour of customers of the organized retail service industry.
4. To analyze the influences of sales promotions on customer purchase intention.
5. To analyze the customers satisfaction level with regards to sales promotional tools adopted by

organized retail service industry.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- There are no significant influences of sales promotional tools on customer purchase intention.
- Customers are not satisfied with sales promotional tools adopted by the organized retail service industry.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

DATA SOURCE

The study was based on both the primary and the secondary data. The secondary data was accumulated from books, journals, magazines, websites and other published sources available in Pune. A structured interview has been taken from personnel of 'more.' to know the sales promotion tools adopted by them. Utilizing the information from secondary data, a structured questionnaire was prepared for customers to accumulate the primary data, comprising closed ended questions. The questionnaire was tested by conducting a pilot study of a few customers selected on random basis. Utilizing the insight from pilot study, questionnaire was modified for the final study. This primary data was collected from customers of 'more.' For descriptive and exploratory research were used in compiling this study. While exploratory research helped in developing the hypotheses through analysis of secondary data, descriptive research was used in order to complete this whole study. Su

method was employed to carry out this study through printed questionnaires by personal interview. Nominal, Ordinal and Likert five point scales are utilized to take the response of respondents. Location of Research was Talegaon of Pune district of Maharashtra state. Simple percentage method has been used to analyze the demographic and behavioral characteristics of respondents. Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test has been applied to know degree of agreement and satisfaction of respondents. It is similar to Chi Square Test, test of goodness of fit.

SAMPLING PLAN

Customers of 'more' were selected on random basis from their customers when they visited their outlet on week days. The questionnaires were distributed simultaneously among 200 respondents during October and November 2009. Survey was done in all seven days, but we specially surveyed on Saturday and Sunday. For the purpose of this survey, Random Sampling of Probability Sampling Technique has been employed as it gives every unit of the population a known and non-zero probability of being selected.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- Study was limited with one organized retailer named as: 'more.'
- Study was limited to a few customers selected on random basis.
- Frauds/fault in giving the right information can not be neglected.

- Due to short of time and resources the study was confined to only a selected region of Pune.

ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION AND FINDINGS

Study was divided into five main headings-

1) VARIOUS SALES PROMOTIONAL TOOLS ADOPTED BY 'more'

Table 1.1 summarizes various sales promotion tools used by 'more.' to promote sales in the month of October and November 2009. A personal interview has been taken of personnel of 'more.' to know all these tools. In which 'clubmore.' membership scheme is used to build customers loyalty. In this scheme member customers get 10 points on the purchase of Rs. 100. These points are redeemable in terms of discount of Rs. 25 when the total points will be 500. Monthly shopping scheme helps to insist customers to purchase more in a particular month to get free gifts. Limited offers scheme is employed to stimulate sales suddenly by offering discount for a particular period of time. Best buys of the month scheme attracts customers towards the company's own brand by giving extra discounts. Buy and get free schemes is utilized to increase the sale of specific products which are lagging their sales. Discount on bulk purchase is to entice the customers to purchase extra. Combo pack scheme is to increase the sale of specific items. Exclusive schemes for 'clubmore.' members are to allure the customers to be

a member of 'more.'. Free samples are distributed but only of the own label brands to test them among the customers. Free gifts on purchase of specific products, gift hampers on special occasions to loyal customers are provided by 'more'. If any customer make a purchase of Rs. 8000/- in the two months with a single or multiple bill, customer can avail free gift of Rs 800/-. 'more.' offers discount on specific products, bulk purchase and combo-pack. 'more.' tempts member customers by price off as well as earned point and extra points on purchase of specific items. 'more.' also conducts contests like lucky draw. Apart from these tools 'more.' uses some additional tools like free home delivery and SMS alerts to members about discounts/schemes.

2) ANALYSIS OF DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF RESPONDENTS

To analyze the demographic variables of respondents, responses have been taken on nominal and ordinal scales. Table 2.1 delineates 51.5%

Table 1.1 : Various Sales Promotional Tools adopted by 'more.'

Sr. No.	Sales Promotional Tools	
1)	Schemes	a) Clubmore. membership Scheme
		b) Monthly Shopping Scheme
		c) Limited Offers Scheme
		d) Best Buys of the Month Scheme
		e) Buy & Get Free Scheme
		f) Discount on Bulk Purchase Scheme
		g) Combo pack Discount Scheme
		h) Exclusive Schemes for Clubmore. members
2)	Free Samples	a) Yes, but only of the few more.'s owned brand
3)	Gifts	a) Free gift on purchase of specific items
		b) Gift hampers on special occasions like festivals
		c) Shop for Rs. 8000/- in a particular period and get free gift
4)	Rebates	a) Discounts on purchase of specific items
		b) Discount on bulk Purchase
		c) Combopack discount
5)	Prizes	a) Save rupees and earned point
		b) Get extra points on purchase of specific items
6)	Contest	a) Lucky Draw
7)	Additional Tools	a) Free home delivery
		b) SMS alerts to members about discounts & schemes

respondents were male and 48.5% respondents were female in which majority of the respondents (82%) were married. Majority of the respondents (48%) belonged to age group of 31-50 and most of the respondents (62%) were well educated. Majority of respondents (63%) were working in which most of

respondents (43.5%) were salaried. Majority of the respondents (85.5) were belonged to income group more than one lakh per annum. Majority of the respondents (74.5%) were belonged to nuclear family in which most of the respondents (68.5%) had 2-5 members in their family.

3) ANALYSIS OF BEHAVIORAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

To find out the behavioral characteristics of respondents, responses have been received on nominal and ordinal scales. Table 3.1 and table 3.2 delineates majority of respondents (60%) took their purchase making decisions by self. Majority of the respondents (51%) collected the information while purchase making decisions in which most of the respondents (43%) collected the information from advertising, other majority (41%) from neighbors/friends/relatives, and other majority (34%) from family members. Majority of respondents (83.7%) collected the information from

Table 2.1 : Descriptive Statistics of Demographic Variables of Respondents

Sr. No.	Variable	Sub-Variable	Frequency	(Percentage %)
1)	Gender	Male	103	51.5
		Female	97	48.5
2)	Age (Years)	< 21	23	11.5
		21- 30	36	18.0
		31-40	55	27.5
		41-50	41	20.5
		51-60	27	13.5
		> 60	18	9.0
3)	Marital Status	Single	36	18.0
		Married	164	82.0
4)	Education Status	Illiterate	5	2.5
		Below 10th	18	9.0
		10th to 12th	53	26.5
		Graduation	64	32.0
		Post Graduation	60	30.0
5)	Working Nature	Yes	126	63.0
		No	74	37
6)	Occupation Status	Student	18	9.0
		Salaried	87	43.5
		Own Business	39	19.5
		House Wife	42	21.0
		Other	14	7.0
7)	Family Income (Yearly)	< 1 Lakh	29	14.5
		1 - 2 Lakhs	86	43.5
		2 - 5 Lakhs	62	31.0
		> 5 Lakhs	23	11.5
8)	Nature of Family	Nuclear	149	74.5
		Joint	51	25.5
9)	Family Size	2 -3 Members	46	23.0
		4-5 Members	91	45.5
		6-7 Members	49	24.5
		> 7 Members	14	7.0
Total			200	100%

Television, other majority (70.9%) from Newspaper, and other majority (37.2%) from pamphlets among majority of information collected from advertising. Most of respondents (79%) visited retail outlet more than 3 times in a month in which majority of the respondents (44%) spend Rs. 2000-5000 per month and majority of the respondents (51%) purchased the quantity for duration of one week. Majority of the

respondents' purchase making decisions (68.5% influenced by family members, other majority (60% by self, other majority (48%) by neighbors/friends/relatives, and other majority (44% by sales promotion. Most of respondents (53.5% purchased all types of products like fruits, vegetable grocery, frozen foods, beverages, home and personal care. Table 3.3 delineates most of respondents

Table 3.1 : Descriptive Statistics of Behavioral Characteristics of Respondents

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Sub-Characteristics	Frequency	(Percentage %)
1)	Purchase Making Decision	Self	120	60.0
		Other	80	40.0
2)	Information Collection Decision	Yes	102	51.0
		No	98	49.0
3)	Frequency to visit outlet (Monthly)	1 Time	7	3.5
		2 Times	18	9.0
		3 Times	17	8.5
		4 Times	59	29.5
		> 4 times	99	49.5
4)	Money Spend (Monthly)	< Rs. 1000	32	16.0
		Rs. 1000-2000	54	27.0
		Rs. 2001-5000	88	44.0
		> Rs. 5000	26	13.0
5)	Quantity Purchased for a Duration	1 week	102	51.0
		2 week	52	26.0
		3 week	27	13.5
		> 3 week	19	9.5
Total			200	100%

(55.5%) we brand an quality conscious an other majori (44.5%) we interested price discount schemes an quantity.

Table 3.2 : Descriptive Statistics of other Behavioral Characteristics of Respondents

1)	Sources of Information Collection	Advertising	86	43.0
		Family Members	68	34.0
		Neighbors/Friends/Relatives	82	41.0
		Others	25	12.5
2)	Source of Information from Advertising	Television	61	70.9
		Newspapers	72	83.7
		Magazines	14	16.3
		Hoardings	18	20.9
		Pamphlets	32	37.2
		Others	12	14.0
		3)	Sources of Influencing Buying Decision	Self
Family Members	137			68.5
Neighbors/Friends/Relatives	97			48.5
Advertising	73			36.5
Sales Promotion	88			44.0
4)	Types of Products Purchased	Fruits	29	14.5
		Vegetables	36	18.0
		Grocery	62	31.0
		Frozen Foods	14	7.0
		Beverages	27	13.5
		Home Care	51	25.5
		Personal Care	47	23.5
		All	103	51.5

Table 3.3 : Cross Tabulation of Preference of Respondents

Preference	Brand	Quality	Price	Discount	Scheme	Quantity	Total
1 st	62	49	31	23	19	16	200
2 nd	40	53	39	31	27	10	200
3 rd	35	39	43	48	21	14	200
4 th	29	22	33	34	39	43	200
5 th	21	17	25	28	51	58	200
6 th	13	20	29	36	43	59	200
Total	200	200	200	200	200	200	1200

4) ANALYSIS TO FINDOUT THE INFLUENCES OF SALES PROMOTIONS ON CUSTOMER PURCHASE INTENTION

To analyze the influences of sales promotions on customer purchase intention, some relevant statements were asked to rate on Likert five point scales ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. To find out the degree of agreement between a set of value observed and values specified by the null hypothesis, Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample Test has been applied. Table 4.1 delineates calculated Kolmogorov-Smirnov D Value for each Statement. The critical value of D at an alpha of 0.05 is 0.096. As the calculated D exceeds the critical value of 0.096, the null hypothesis that there are no significant influences of sales promotions on customer purchase intention is

Table 4.1 : Kolmogorov-Smirnov D Value for each Statement (Agreement Scale)

Sr. No.	Statements	D Value
1	Sales Promotions influence customer purchase intention.	0.20
2	Sales Promotions increase customer satisfaction level.	0.18
3	Sales Promotions affect the frequency to visit outlet.	0.17
4	Sales Promotions play a vital role to spend more.	0.17
5	Sales Promotions entice to repurchase.	0.16
6	Customers purchase more quantity due to sales promotions.	0.19
7	'more.' does adequate sales promotion activities.	0.13
8	'more.' justifies its punch line: "Hamesha Extra"	0.10

rejected.

Chart 4.2 delineates majority of respondents (83%) were accepted that sales promotions allure them to visit 'more.' super market.

Chart 4.2

Chart 4.3 delineates majority of respondents (62%) were loyal with 'more.', but other majority (38%) were accepted that other retailers' sales promotion allure them to visit their outlet.

Chart 4.3

5)

ANALYSIS TO FIND OUT SATISFACTION LEVEL OF CUSTOMERS WITH REGARD TO SALES PROMOTIONAL TOOLS ADOPTED BY 'more.'

To analyze the satisfaction level of customer some relevant sales promotional tools adopted 'more.' were asked to rate on Likert five point scale ranging from highly dissatisfy to highly satisfy. find out the degree of satisfaction between a set of value observed and values specific

Table 5.1 : Kolmogorov-Smirnov D Value for each Variable (Satisfaction Scale)

Sr. No.	Variable	Kolmogorov-Smirnov D Value
1	Overall Schemes	0.20
2	Clubmore, membership Scheme	0.17
3	Monthly Shopping Scheme	0.16
4	Limited Offers Scheme	0.15
5	Best Buys of the Month Scheme	0.17
6	Buy & Get Free Scheme	0.13
7	Discount on Bulk Purchase Scheme	0.16
8	Combo pack Discount Scheme	0.14
9	Exclusive Schemes for Clubmore, members	0.18
10	Free samples	0.10
11	Gifts	0.14
12	Rebates	0.18
13	Prizes	0.16
14	Contest	0.12
15	Additional promotional tools	0.12
16	Over all sales promotion activities	0.21

by the null hypothesis, Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample Test has been applied. Table 5.1 delineates calculated Kolmogorov-Smirnov D Value for each variable. The critical value of D at an alpha of 0.05 is 0.096. As the calculated D exceeds the critical value of 0.096, the null hypothesis that customers are not satisfied with sales promotional tools adopted by organized retail industry is rejected.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we could find out that sales promotions entice customers, increase their satisfaction, play a vital role to spend more, increase the frequency to visit, encourage purchasing more quantity and tempts to repurchase. On the basis of above discussion, we can say that sales promotions have significant influences on customer purchase intention. We also find out that customers of organized retail industry are satisfied with the various sales promotional tools adopted like different schemes- membership scheme, monthly and limited offers scheme, best buys of the month scheme, buy & get free scheme, discount on bulk purchase scheme, combo- pack discount scheme, and exclusive schemes for loyal/member customers; free gifts; rebates; prizes; contests and some additional tools- free home delivery, SMS alerts to members about discounts and schemes. But customers suggested some more promotional tools like deposit schemes with guaranteed rebates, coupons redeemable on next purchase, exchange offers scheme, more free samples

and some additional tools like internet billing facility, insurance cover to loyal customers, more effective SMS alerts to members.

Today retailing is much more than mere merchandising. It is about reflecting customer's expectations, aspirations and furnishing the long lasting relationship with them. As we know, in contemporary marketing scenario consumer is king and satisfaction of consumer is the prime goal/function of organized retailers. Role of women has been changed a lot in our society because of increase in literacy level and working women population in India. Now they not only manage the house but also participate in purchase making decisions of the family. Apart from innovative product and services, smart marketing, aggressive advertising and distribution strategies; some innovative, aggressive, effective, attractive and competitive sales promotions strategies are today's demand for effective delivery, targeting, and satisfying consumer needs in the best manner in organized retail industry. Customer's anticipations are very high from organized retailers. So the organized retail industry have to fulfill all these anticipations in order to flourish, thrive, and germinate by laps and bounce in the Indian market.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study can be justified in the following ways: the study furnishes information about- the different sales

promotional tools adopted by the organized retail industry, changing buying behaviour of the customers, influences of sales promotions on customers purchase intention, and the satisfaction level of customers with regards to these sales promotional tools. The study also helps the responsible management of organized retailers to formulate more effective and attractive sales promotional strategies to attract new customers, increase satisfaction level of customers and beat competitions. The study will further prove to be of great help to the researchers/management students who want to do similar or related study in the future.

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